
Notebooks as instrument for awareness raising
on CoARA commitments

RAPP-JR Methodological Report

Gerit Anders, Helene Schiffbänker

Funded by
the European Union

CoARA Boost CF1

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation program under Grant Agreement No. 101131826

Table of contents

Table of contents	2
Abstract	3
Introduction	4
Context: JR as research organisation in applied research	4
Methodology	5
Study process	6
Digital notebooks as instrument for awareness raising	7
Main Findings	7
Scientific excellence	7
Recruitment	9
Open science	10
Conclusion	12
List of References	13

Abstract

This paper is an outcome of the RAPP-JR project, which has been funded by the CoARA Boost Call 1. The project aimed to develop a way of reforming assessment approaches and practices in the research organisation JR in line with the CoARA commitments.

Among other methods, a digital notebook study has been conducted. This is a participative method which is well suited to make employees reflect on existing practices. Through that, awareness on the possibilities of reforming the three topics chosen in RAPP-JR - scientific excellence, recruitment and open science – can be raised.

This paper presents the methodology, the results and the potential of this method to raise awareness.

Introduction

The following paper is a result of the project RAPP-JR (Reforming Assessment Processes and Practices at JOANNEUM RESEARCH), which objective was to develop a way of reforming assessment approaches and practices in JR (JOANNEUM RESEARCH) in line with the CoARA commitments. The activities therefore aimed, on the one hand, at raising awareness for the CoARA commitments and the necessity to reform research assessment approaches at all organisational levels and, on the other hand, at developing concrete ideas for the reform. One of the activities conducted in course of the project is the digital notebook study. In this paper we aim to introduce notebook writing as an instrument to raise awareness within a research organisation. By presenting the approach, the results and by highlighting the potential of this method for awareness raising, we hope to make this method useable for other CoARA beneficiaries.

The paper is structured as follows: We start with introducing the organisational context of the project. We continue with a chapter about the methodology before we summarise the results obtained from applying this method. Finally, we draw some methodological conclusions for further use of notebooks in CoARA context and for stimulating organisational change.

Context: JR as research organisation in applied research

JR¹ is a research performance organisation in Austria with seven research institutes covering a wide range of different research fields and more than 500 employees. The main business is contract research and funded research whereby the focus lays on applied research. In this context circumstances and practices differ from the university context, however, research assessment approaches mostly don't consider these differences.

Therefore, in course of the RAPP-JR project one aim was to capture the particularities in this context and identify specific needs and circumstances in the context of applied research to be able to base the ideas for reformation on this specific context and encourage a discussion about it in the national and international community.

For the RAPP-JR project, three topics have been chosen to focus attention on:

- Scientific excellence
- Recruitment
- Open Science

For these topics the project aimed to capture the existing structures and practices to identify the reform needs and possibilities.

Formal Excellence at JR: The assessment system for scientific excellence currently in place at JR encompasses a wide range of indicators, which cover the areas scientificity, invention disclosures and

¹ <https://www.joanneum.at/en/>

human resources. These indicators are measured for all institutes in the same way, although the notebook study has revealed not all indicators are relevant for all disciplines. For example, inventions disclosures are mostly relevant for technical institutes but not for others. And vice versa are publications, committees and reviews rather relevant for fields which are closer to academic research but not that important for most technical field.

Recruitment at JR: Efforts to make career paths and recruitment processes at JR as fair as possible have been underway for some time, since the company has already a lot of experience in gender equality policy. The diversity department at JR have developed a gender-sensitive recruitment guide, which defines the entire recruitment process and aims to assure that this process is fair and leaves to space for discrimination of any kind. Further, in this topic the internal assessment approaches of measuring the performance of employed researchers and the defined career paths play a role. JR has defined internally career paths for scientific staff that foresee two paths, one towards a purely scientific career and one towards research management.

Open Science at JR: When it comes to open science it must be differentiated in the context of JR between contract research and funding research, the two main business areas. On the one hand, open science is increasingly important in funding research and on the other hand, scientists engaged in contract research face severe restrictions in this regard.

Methodology

Raising awareness is a central element of effective change management, because respective individuals and groups need to understand why change is necessary in order to engage meaningfully with it (see Weiner 2009). Without this initial awareness of the need for change and the potential benefits of new ways of working, employees are more likely to resist or passively comply rather than actively support change efforts. Research shows that understanding employees' perceptions including their recognition of existing practices is important for navigating change processes and mitigating resistance, which often arises from uncertainty, fear of the unknown, or comfort with familiar routines. Moreover, it is essential to identify and reflect on existing practices and assumptions as a baseline for change, since recognising current behaviours helps to see what must be preserved versus altered in the change process (see Hubbart 2023).

In the context of the RAPP-JR project, we intentionally applied a method that creates structured space for staff to reflect deeply on specific CoARA topics despite a high workload and enable them to articulate their current assumptions, an approach that aligns with the idea that readiness and commitment to change are built through understanding both present conditions and the rationale for change (see Weiner 2009). The digital notebook method fulfils exactly this purpose and is therefore a crucial method in the context of the RAPP-JR project.

This method is an adaptation of the digital diary study. The digital diary is a qualitative method which collects information remotely over a longer period of time. It is often used when behaviour and opinions of costumers, users or other target groups are the epistemological interest. In contrast, in other qualitative methods such as interviews or focus groups, data is always collected situation-based which

means the data depends on the time and space the method takes place and therefore is more a snapshot. In diary studies, participants self-report their thoughts independently of time, space and the observer, they are only provided with instructions and support. This method is promising when time plays a crucial role, and also it is favourable that participants are able to choose the moment for reflection by themselves. Further, they avoid the risk that the observer would influence the data (see Moran 2018).

In course of RAPP-JR, the project team aimed to gather information about JR researchers' individual thoughts about assessment criteria in general and how they personally aim to be assessed based on their work experience. This process of reflection is supposed to make participants think about aspects they would not think about otherwise. This method was promising because it enables participants to reflect on specific topics and questions independently and over a longer period.

The project team decided to call the method 'Notebooks' instead of 'Diary' as it is a simplified form of the diary study method. Also, in the professional context the term "notebook" felt more suitable than "diary". In the literature, an interposed approach to diary studies is recommended, where qualitative interviews are suggested with the study participants before and after the diary-writing phase (see Jarrahi et.al. 2021). This approach has been applied in RAPP-JR in a similar way: group meetings have been conducted before the data collection phase to instruct the participants how to conduct their tasks. After the data collections phase one collective reflection workshop was organised to share experiences and to identify common pattern as well as diverging observations.

Study process

The recruitment of the notebook writers started at the kick-off workshop of the RAPP-JR project with the scientific staff at JR. The participants of this event (about 20) have been asked actively if they would be interested in becoming a notebook writer. Further efforts to recruit notebook writers have been made by the equal opportunities' officers at the various JR institutes who encouraged researchers to participate

In the end, 11 researchers representing all departments at JR have been recruited as notebook writers. The notebook-writing phase has been scheduled for April 2025. Beforehand participants were provided with instructions and guiding questions for the writing process. This guideline has been developed based on the document analysis and along the three topics addressed in RAPP (excellence, careers, open science). The notebook writers could choose if they would cover all three topics or only one or two in case the others are of limited relevance in their daily life.

A Q&A Session was offered after the first writing week, the discussed challenges and solutions were summarised in a Q&A document which was shared with all participants. The project team supported the participants also during the writing process.

As suggested by Jarrahi et.al. (2021) a reflection workshop with all notebook writers took place in May 2025 after the writing phase of four weeks in April. In preparation for this workshop the notebooks underwent an initial analysis to be able to link the discussion in the workshop directly to the topics and challenges outlined in the notebooks. The workshop had a participatory nature and provided space for input from the project team as well as free discussion. For the provided the content of the notebooks has

been summarised and presented to all participants first, to bring everyone up to the same level of knowledge and second, to make participants aware of the challenges faced by other disciplines but their own. This provided input was the basis for the discussion between the participants. The workshop was structured along the three topics as well as the notebook guidelines.

The collected notebooks were anonymised and analysed by the project team. Also, the outcomes of the reflection workshop were included in this analysis. MAXQDA was used for content analysis.

Digital notebooks as instrument for awareness raising

Conducting this method at an early phase of the project has been found to fit well to raise awareness on the topic and the CoARA commitments among the scientific staff at JR. First, the participants in this notebook study represented all institutes at JR and therefore the perspectives from different disciplines were captured and involved. Second, especially because this method allows participants to reflect on a topic for a longer period, a process of change in the perspective is more likely than it would be with a method that is conducted to one specific time. The guidelines for the participants included main and sub-questions related to the objectives set by CoARA.

Not only the notebook writing itself supported awareness raising, but also the reflection workshop played a crucial role in this regard. After a period in which the participants reflected on the topics themselves, they came together to discuss their ideas once again. This created a common understanding among these individuals, who come from different scientific backgrounds. The study participants not only reflected on practices in their own fields, but also engaged in interdisciplinary exchange, which generated new ideas and raised awareness on various levels.

Main Findings

The following chapter sums up the insights gathered through the analysis of the notebooks and this reflection workshop. The results are presented along the three main topics of the RAPP-JR project, as the notebooks as well as the reflection workshop has been constructed along them.

I Scientific excellence

Notebook writers reflected their understanding of scientific excellence in the context of a non-university research organisation in applied research. An excellent researcher is described as being prestigious and well established in one's scientific field, with that involving different activities. An important aspect is international recognition, which manifests itself in invitations to give lectures, invitations for publications, invitation to be a reviewer or a supervisor, as an indication of scientific excellence.

The writers are aware of the problem with established indicators like number of publications, rankings or impact factors in journals as these indicators can easily be artificially improved; tend to favour already established scientists, institutes or methods. It was stated that scientific excellence at JR does not only

mean publications, but also acquisition of research funds, dissemination of knowledge and results, teaching and supervising activities. However, these aspects are harder to measure.

Applied research is the core business of all institutes at JR. This context has different requirements in research assessment compared to universities. Most scientists at JR see a **critical discourse** on excellence as important. Applied research is practically and purposefully oriented and therefore always in line with public interests. In this context, **funding** is the indicator for success rather than publications. In most research projects **publications** are **not** even **possible** or not desired for different reasons (not considered in the project budget, limitations due to (industry) project partners). Therefore, the number of publications or impact factors are indicators with limited relevance for scientific excellence in that domain. Based on their daily work experiences, an indicator that measures the success rate of funding acquisition or successful delivered contract research projects could rather cover what researchers understand as excellence.

Applied research also goes hand in hand with a different way of working, from which success criteria can also be derived. Work is structured in projects; researchers mostly work in groups and address socially relevant problems often with an interdisciplinary approach. Therefore, measuring the **societal relevance** of a research project or the **level of interdisciplinarity** may be more appropriate indicators for excellence in applied research.

It was emphasised that researchers at JR are mostly assessed as a group. Therefore, the internal understandings of excellence and success shape the performance of the group. Therefore, **internal communication and support is** seen as **crucial for success**. Every member of the group is expected to participate in the process of improving and reflecting the way of working together. In that sense it is important how junior researchers are treated within the group, how knowledge is passed on and how the group deals with mistakes and uncertainties in the research process. What was also mentioned in the notebooks is that not every person in a research group has the same chance to achieve JR excellence indicators (see above). Higher ranked researchers and those in leadership positions are more likely to participate in publications, lectures and presentations than lower ranked researchers. That fact makes mentoring programs and supervision of junior researchers crucial for a fair and inclusive research process.

Reform ideas

For these issues, two main ideas to reform the assessment system at JR to make it more suitable for the research practices and the environment in applied research have been discussed by the notebook writers.

- Because JR covers a **variety of research fields**, it is not promising to compare them by the same quantity of indicators. It would be better to consider the differences between institutes and research fields by assessing the performance. One idea that would foster that could be to **measure the quality of contributions** rather than the quantity. This could mean measure the success rate of funding awards, measuring the quality of publications and the relevance of lectures and to establish an indicator for the social relevance or the grade of interdisciplinary of research projects.

- Because research is structured in projects and researchers work in groups, it is promising to focus on the **internal communication** and intensively work on improving it. That could mean establishing **exchange formats for scientists** which enable people within one research group or across research groups to discuss problems, approaches, to reflect on mistakes and work actively together to improve working processes. What is also important in this context is again to support supervision of younger researchers through more experienced researcher. At JR a mentoring system and buddy systems are already established, these existing structures could be developed further and its usage of could be supported by incentives.

II Recruitment

The main message in the notebooks regarding that topic is that generalised assessment criteria in the recruitment process are not desirable. Rather, the assessment criteria should be adjusted to the specific job advertisement.

For every position it should be defined, which social and professional competences are required. Therefore, notebook writers reflected that scientific excellence should only be a criterion for leadership positions and senior researchers, but at the same time they wish that social and soft skills would be given greater consideration in filling these positions. In general, working at JR with mostly interdisciplinary approaches, the ability to be flexible and adaptive is considered favourable from all notebook writers. Therefore, for junior researchers or technicians, scientific excellence should not play a big role, but rather how open-minded applicants are and how motivated to tackle new challenges.

Taking diversity into account in the recruitment process is generally considered positively. They made the experience that different approaches are fruitful for the research process and for working together in a team. Nevertheless, limits are also mentioned. While sectoral and disciplinary mobility is considered positively, because it is favourable for applied research, geographic mobility is seen critical in some contexts. As language- and cultural differences are seen as an obstacle to cooperation within a research group. Further, notebook writers reflected that women at JR are still underrepresented in leadership positions.

Reform ideas

From these reflections, the following suggestions regarding the recruitment process have been made:

- Notebook writers reflected on their own experience with mistakes and all of them concluded that mistakes and failures lead to learnings. Failures cannot be avoided completely, and they always open the possibility to learn something out of it. Based on these experiences, **notebook writers desire a learning culture within the company and hope that researchers become more motivated to exchange about failures and how to deal with it.** Part of this discussion is also how researchers deal with negative outcomes, as failures can be educational on personal level, negative outcomes could lead to important insights for the scientific community, however mostly they are withheld. One idea that addresses these considerations in recruitment is a **narrative CV**. This would give applicants the opportunity to express their career in a different way and show things like mistakes or failures that would otherwise get no space.

- To encourage women to take on management positions, the already existing **mentoring system** at JR should be fostered. In addition to that, **women should be supported to assume project lead positions.**
- Good experiences have been made with **two-step recruitment processes.** The first step would be a classical interview with the leadership and a second step a meeting with the possible future colleagues, which enables the research team to participate in the recruitment process and makes it to estimate if **the applicant fits in the group.**

III Open science

Notebooks made clear that major differences exist between institutes and research fields regarding open science practices. The institutes deal with different areas of open science and have different circumstances and challenges depending on their research field. Therefore, open science is differentiated here in the most relevant areas in the JR context. Overall, it needs to be noted that notebook writers see an ascending relevance of open science aspects since it is increasingly required by RFOs on national and on EU level.

Open access research

Open access research concerns all 7 institutes in different ways. However, as already explained, publication of research results is not equally important for all research fields. Therefore, obviously open access research is more relevant to those who are more eager to publish their results. Additionally, notebook writers argued that not all research projects at JR are suitable to be published. For example, outcomes of contract research projects cannot be published because of confidentiality obligations. Researchers have to estimate which projects and aspect of studies can be published and where it is worth to put additional resources in the publication of results.

On the one hand, publishing articles in open access journals is seen critical because of a lack of quality assurance in some journals. On the other hand, JR has collaborations with selected open access journals that are trustworthy and, based on experiences, fulfil quality criteria, like a professional and transparent review process.

Open data

Regarding the publication of research data, technical fields have more experience than social or health sciences. On the one hand, in the technical field researchers are aware of the benefits of open data for scientific discourse and motivated to publish their data, unless corporate secrets or non-disclosure agreements hinder them. On the other hand, social and health sciences deal a lot with personal data, which have to be anonymized before publishing and therefore data disclosure is more complicated in this field. Although researchers in these disciplines see a benefit in disclose research data for the scientific communities, they might either not be able to due to a lack of resources for data preparation or the data set would loose most of the valuable information through anonymization and therefore disclosure would not be worth it. Additionally, regardless of the discipline, data disclosure goes along with maintenance, and this requires time **resources, which often are not covered by the project budget** either.

In sum, researchers see the benefit of open data, but it requires resources which are often not available in applied research. In addition to that, researchers are often uncertain if data disclosure would make sense, considering the challenges and the additional effort needed. However, in the notebooks it has also been reflected that this uncertainty might not only be a challenge but also a chance for researchers to actively shape future processes of data disclosure. Researchers would like support in disclosing and utilising public data, since there is often uncertainty about which platforms are trustworthy.

Open-source software

Notebook writers reflected that the usage of open-source software is beneficial for scientific practises in general. Besides the practical benefit of it, it enables discourse and communication within the scientific community and opens possibilities for cooperation with different entities.

In technical fields, providing open-source software is connoted with similar challenges than providing open data, **it requires additional effort for maintenance**, for which resources are often not available.

Scientific communication

In course of the topic open science, notebook writers also reflected on scientific communication in general. Here notebook writers reflected that it must be differentiated which focus group should be addressed by scientific communication. Depending on that, different media formats are favourable. For example, elder public society needs to be addressed through newspaper, radio or television and younger public society needs to be addressed rather through social media and the scientific community itself obviously needs to be addressed through its own channels. In scientific communication with the public, researchers are often concerned that information is abridged or used politically.

Further, notebook writers do not agree whether scientific communication should be a criterion for scientific excellence, which means that it is also not equally relevant for all disciplines.

Reform ideas

Generally, regarding open science the following ideas have been generated:

- One suggestion that notebook writers agreed on is to **foster these existing collaborations** and **communicate** the existing opportunities **more intensively** to researchers.
- At JR a template for data management plans has been developed and notebook writers see that as an important step towards efficient data management, which would enable data disclosure in further consequence. Therefore, **institute internal exchange about storage and usage of data and data management plans would be beneficial to deal with discipline-specific challenges**.
- Generally, notebook writers as representatives of scientific staff at JR would benefit from companywide guidelines regarding open science issues, opportunities to get legal support and an exchange format to discuss the topic freely.

Conclusion

Using digital notebooks as methodology in the context of awareness raising for CoARA commitments has been found a suitable approach. Scientific staff at JR has been involved, this being the basis for stimulating organisational change, as pointed out by Hubbart (2023). It has turned out that the notebook method is (i) a good instrument to make people reflect on specific topics which concerns them personally and (ii) the data collection over a period of time allows a broad and deep reflection and subsequently enables a change in thinking.

The project team experienced a slight change in the participants awareness from the beginning of the notebook study until the end and even participants themselves reported that this reflection phase of four weeks, where they wrote their notebook, made them reflect on the existing structures more critically and brought new ideas.

Notebooks can be recommended for further use to other CoARA signatories as well. In the following, an exchange of experiences would be beneficial, highlighting the strengths and potential pitfalls of the approach.

List of References

Hubbart, J. A. (2023). Organizational Change: The Challenge of Change Aversion. *Administrative Sciences*, 13(7), 162. <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci13070162>

Jarrahi, M.H., Goay, C., Zirker, S., & Zhang, Y. "Using Digital Diaries as a Research Method for Capturing Practices in Situ." (2021) In G. Symon., K. Prichard., & C. Hine (Eds.), *Research Methods for Digital Work and Organization: Investigating Distributed, Multi-Modal, and Mobile Work*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Moran, K. „Diary studies: a quick primer” (2018) <https://uxdesign.cc/diary-studies-cd65a61a4f89>; last access 24th of July 2025.

Schiffbaenker, H., & Anders, G. (2025). CoARA Boost CF1-RAPP-JR-D3.1 guidelines and context. Zenodo.<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17913298>

Weiner, B.J. "A theory of organizational readiness for change." (2009) *Implementation Sci* 4, 67. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1748-5908-4-67>

JOANNEUM RESEARCH
Forschungsgesellschaft mbH
Leonhardstrasse 59
8010 Graz
Phone +43 316 876-0
Fax +43 316 876-1181
pr@joanneum.at
www.joanneum.at